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REFLECTING ON THE LESSON CONDUCTED AT THE STATE UNIVERSITY

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Abstract: *In this article I will talk about my lesson I have conducted with a group of junior students in a public university. The students' level of the English language is early intermediate. The language of instruction is English, but Russian and Uzbek is also used to explain words or expressions difficult to interpret. Some steps of successful lesson were described and some recommendations were given.*

Keywords: *lesson plan, critical evaluation, relative clauses, learning objectives.*

Introduction

Lesson objectives are really essential and it leads to design a good lesson plan (Kelly, 2023). They will explicitly say what students will learn. Lesson objectives include two elements:

- a) The explanation of what students will learn
- b) The methods on how students learning will be evaluated

Here are some examples of learning objectives:

- a) Students will write an essay, an introduction, body and conclusion
- b) Students will outline an essay with related supporting ideas
- c) Students will learn new business vocabulary and use them in practice

Lesson objectives are characterized as SMART (see Figure 1). It stands for specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time bound. LO should be well defined to students and observable to teachers, and these questions words should be answered: who, what, when, where, why. Measurable – objectives can be evaluative and objective. Students can achieve academic objectives. By relevant, students are prepared for standardized tests. By time, students will have enough time to complete assignments.

Development

As it was stated in the lesson's objectives, students would learn new words related to the business and use the structure "relative clauses" while at the same time

develop their listening, reading, speaking and writing skills (Arslonbekova, 2023). Also, they would improve their vocabulary, grammar, group work, pair work, and language skills.

Student learning outcomes were aimed to achieve the following by the end of the lesson:

1. students would be able to notice and use relative clauses construction.
2. they would be able to name specific vocabulary in business.
3. they would be able to read and write words related to the advertisement.
4. they would be able to pronounce and spell correctly words to the topic of “advertisement”.

Figure 1. What are Lesson Objectives

Adopted from YouTube

Before students were introduced about *relative clauses* grammar structure and some advertisement words were introduced to the students and the lesson in focus was organised to help students better practice some vocabulary through a variety of exercises like watching a video, doing activities with the focus on vocabulary, spelling, and understanding the meaning of new words in the Russian language (Akhmadjonov, 2023).

Step 1. Preparation.

Before the teaching, I went to the classroom earlier to prepare for the lesson. I checked the devices and got everything ready before students' arrival. I checked the content in the lesson plan from beginning to the end and decided on some changes.

Then students came and we started to greet each other. Since I have seen them already, I started to approach each of them and asked about their daily life. Allday and Pakurar (2007) found out that teachers greeting could improve student on-task behaviour. In simple words, students with poor behaviour can be encouraged to focus on tasks as teachers are kind and respectful to them.

Step 2. Review and Revision

First of all, I commenced the class with the revision of the expressions studied in the previous lesson. I read some words from a student's copybook and randomly asked students to translate them from Russian into English during which every student was active. In general, students managed with the activity quite well. The purpose of the activity was to help students better understand and identify words with correct pronunciation.

Step 3. Spelling activity

The next activity aimed at identifying correct words and writing them with proper spelling and was organised by distributing handouts with an exercise to match the vocabulary and the definitions. The exercise was interesting and easy for students and they showed great enthusiasm through raising their hands and shouting out.

Step 4. Video activity

The next video activity helped students develop their listening comprehension, understanding written English and writing skills were also in the focus. The students were eager to watch the video. In order to achieve our objectives, I handed in some handouts for the video task. The instructions were read to the video exercises together with the students in order to explain them what they were supposed to do while and after watching. The instructions were to read individually and translate them into Russian by students as a comprehension check. The students' level of English was enough to understand all details in the exercise, so the group translation of the instructions was not employed. The exercises for the video activity had different questions types such as true/false, matching, memory test of ads, posters, and vocabulary and sentence completion.

Step 5. Group work

The next activity was a group work task which had multiple aims: to encourage students to work together, to improve their communicative, writing, competing skills and sharing knowledge with friends. The task asked students to fill in the spaces with

words they had learnt about the topic “advertisement”. I have grouped students into two: one with males and females and another with only males. The words activity was so exciting that all students looked competitive and very motivated. During the activity I helped two groups to cope with the words motivating, explaining some words, and directing.

Step 6. Skills development

The final activity aimed at developing speaking and creative thinking skills and was organised through asking students to come to the blackboard with their home task that was to draw a scheme of their advertisement and describe their drawings using relative clauses and vocabulary about ads. Students were presenting one by one describing their posters, ads to other students who were listening to them. I was watching from the back of the classroom and monitoring other students whether they were paying attention to their friends’ descriptions.

Conclusion

To sum up, students who were involved in different activities in the lesson were more motivated than those who were not. In order to encourage students’ teachers should carefully choose teaching materials and engage students with different activities and exercises.

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